

Studies in Organo-Arsenic Compounds. Part III.

BY HIRENDRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

The action of ethylene and acetylene upon chlorides of sulphur, arsenic, antimony and tin has been studied by numerous investigators. Defert (*Monatsh.*, 1919, **40**, 313) obtained a compound by reacting acetylene with arsenic trichloride in the presence of aluminium chloride to which he incorrectly assigned the formula $\text{AsCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_2$. The systematic study of the nature of the reaction products was done by Green and Price (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 448) who showed that three substances of novel types are produced in this reaction, *viz.*, β -Chlorovinyl-dichloroarsine ($\text{Cl}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{AsCl}_2$); $\beta\beta'$ -dichloro-divinylchloroarsine [$(\text{Cl}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH})_2\text{AsCl}$] and $\beta\beta'\beta''$ -trichlorotrivinylarsine [$(\text{Cl}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH})_3\text{As}$]. The results obtained have been confirmed by Mann and Pope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1754). Lewis and Stiegler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 2546) have proved conclusively that the above types of reactions can easily be extended to bromo and iodo derivatives of arsenic. A survey of the literature thus shows that

(a) Acetylene is readily absorbed by halogenated trivalent arsenic derivatives in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

(b) The formation of the different arsines takes place in stages and that with continued bubbling of the gas through the reaction mixture with corresponding diminished temperature, the yield of tertiary arsine increases at the cost of the primary one. If, however, the supply of the gas be stopped after a definite period and the temperature be allowed to increase the yield of the primary arsine increases with corresponding decrease in the proportion of the tertiary arsine till the equilibrium is established.

(c) The halogen attached to β -carbon, containing a double bond, possesses the characteristic stability.

The study of the literature lends strong support to the view that methyl arsenious chloride, in which the arsenic is in the trivalent state and contains chlorine as well, would behave similarly. The present paper describes the action of acetylene on methyl arsenious chloride and as expected two different types of compounds *viz.*,

β -chlorovinyl methylchloroarsine (I) and $\beta\beta'$ -dichlorodivinyl methylarsine (II) have now been isolated. $\beta\beta'$ -Dichlorodivinyl methylarsine has been identified by the formation of identical derivatives (*vide experimental*) of the compound prepared by Lewis and Stiegler (*loc. cit.*) from *bis*- β -chlorovinylchloroarsine. The reactions take place in the following way :—

The behaviour of the chlorine atom attached to the arsenic is analogous to that of other chlorovinyl compounds as it readily gives derivatives like oxide, arsenic acid, sulphide, cyanide, mixed arsine, arsonium compounds, double salt, etc. These compounds are less irritant to the mucous membrane of the nose than the chlorovinyl compounds.

These experiments are in agreement with the fact that acetylene reacts with phenyl arsenious chloride in presence of aluminium chloride and yields two types of compounds, *viz.* Ph.AsCH=CHCl and Ph.As (CH=CHCl)₂ (Das-Gupta, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 627).

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Chlorovinylmethylchloroarsine (I).—Acetylene, washed through saturated solution of sodium bisulphite and dried by concentrated sulphuric acid, was passed for 2 hours through a mixture of methyl dichloroarsine (50 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g.) at 10–15°. The mixture was well stirred throughout and stirring continued for 8 hours more, the temp. not rising above 25°. The brown viscous liquid was decomposed in the cold by 20% hydrochloric acid. The lower thick brown layer was removed, repeatedly washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried over calcium chloride, the ether removed and the brown oil was fractionated at 10 mm. Three fractions were collected: (i) at 45–65°, a colourless oil consisting of a mixture of unchanged original compound and other by-products. (ii) at 110–15°, consist-

ing of the bulk of the desired product (iii) at 140–45°, the tertiary arsiuc. The second fraction was redistilled at 112–15°/10 mm.

It is colourless when freshly distilled but on storage it slowly turns pink. It does not attack the nose so intensively as the parent substance but it produces blister on the skin which takes a long time to heal up. [Found : Cl, 37·2 ; As, 39·95 ; M.W. (cryoscopic), 184·3, 186·1. $C_3H_3Cl_2As$ requires Cl, 37·9 ; As, 40·1 per cent. M. W. 187].

β-Chlorovinylmethylarsinic Acid (ClCH=CHAsMe).

β-Chlorovinylmethylchloroarsine (1 g.) was suspended in water (3 c.c.) and treated with excess of perhydrol. Within a short time a vigorous reaction ensued with rise in temperature. The mixture was heated for some time on water-bath with occasional addition of fresh perhydrol till the oil was all dissolved. The pasty residue was cooled in ice and extracted with a mixture of acetone and ether (1 : 1), colourless crystals of the arsinic acid separated on spontaneous evaporation of the solution. It was recrystallised from acetone, m. p. 149–150° (uncorr.). (Found : Cl, 19·1 ; As, 40·5 : $C_3H_6O_2$ ClAs requires Cl, 19·2 ; As, 40·6 per cent).

β-Chlorovinylmethylarsenious Sulphide.

It was obtained by passing sulphuretted hydrogen through an alcoholic solution of (I) for 1 hour. The solution was filtered from minute traces of yellow precipitate and the filtrate was diluted with water and the oil obtained was washed with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator for 2 days. It is light yellow in colour and is soluble in most of the common organic solvents. (Found : Cl, 20·8 ; As, 44·6. $C_6H_{10}Cl_2As_2S$ requires Cl, 21·19 ; As, 44·7 per cent).

β-Chlorovinylmethylarsenious Cyanide [ClCH=CHAs(CN)Me].—An alcoholic solution of (I) was treated with an aqueous solution of potassium cyanide, when potassium chloride separated with considerable rise in temperature. The filtrate on cooling and dilution with water gave a light yellow oil, which was separated, repeatedly washed

with water and then dried in vacuo. (Found. Cl, 20.5; As, 42.1. C_4H_5NClAs requires Cl, 20.0; As, 42.2 per cent)

β -Chlorovinylmethylarsenious Oxide ($ClCH=CHAsO\cdot AsCH=CHCl$).—An alcoholic solution of (I) was added to an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide when sodium chloride was precipitated. The filtered solution was concentrated, cooled and treated with ether, when silky needles were obtained which were crystallised twice from water and finally from alcohol. (Found. Cl, 22.1, As, 47.2. $C_6H_{10}OCl_2As_2$, requires Cl, 22.2; As, 47.02 per cent).

β -Chlorovinylmethylphenylarsine ($ClCH=CHAs(Me)C_6H_5$).—To the ethereal solution of the Grignard reagent from bromobenzene (5 g.), magnesium (0.8 g.), β -chlorovinyl methylchloroarsine (6 g.) in absolute ether was added drop by drop with stirring. On keeping overnight the mixture was decomposed by ice cold water and the resulting product was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried by calcium chloride and the compound was purified by reprecipitating it several times from ether by alcohol. (Found. Cl, 15.4; As, 32.1. $C_9H_{10}ClAs$ requires Cl, 15.5; As, 32.8 per cent)

$\beta\beta$ -Dichlorovinylmethylarsine (II).—It was obtained in a crude condition in the fraction 140-45°/10 mm. after passing acetylene through methylarsenic chloride (*vide supra*). The oil was repeatedly washed with dilute acid and water, dried and redistilled. It was identified by preparing mercuric chloride double compound [$Cl\cdot CH=CH$]₂AsMe, HgCl₂, m. p. and mixed m. p. with Lewis and Stiegler's comp. 162° (Found. As, 15.5. $C_5H_7Cl_4AsHg$ requires As, 15.4 per cent), and also the arsonium iodide, m. p. and mixed m. p. 243° (decomp.). (Found. As, 21.1. $C_6H_{10}Cl_2IAs$ requires As, 21.1 per cent). (*cf.* Lewis and Stiegler, *loc cit.*)

This compound was also prepared from β -chlorovinyl methylchloroarsine and acetylene in presence of aluminum chloride at a temperature of 5-10° and distilling the resulting product. (Found: As, 35.3. $C_5H_7Cl_2As$ requires As, 35.2 per cent).

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